

On-line Learning, Classification and Interpretation of Brain Signals using 3D SNN and ESN

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Abstract—The paper proposes a novel hierarchical recurrent neural network architecture for on-line classification and interpretation of EEG data. It incorporates two dynamic pools of neurons - one based on NeuCube three dimensional structure of spiking neurons, spatially mapping a brain template and connected via spike-timing dependent plastic synapses and another Echo state neural network (ESN) reservoir of sparsely connected hyperbolic tangent neurons that is able to learn on-line to classify continuously extracted from the Cube spike-rate features. The aim of the work was to interpret and classify in a brain-inspired manner dynamic spatio-temporal brain signals. The achieved results demonstrate improved classification accuracy on a benchmark EEG data set along with a good interpretability of the data. In future, the proposed method can be used for classification of other brain spatio-temporal data, such as ECG and fMRI.

Index Terms—SNN, ESN, NeuCube, EEG, classification, on-line learning, spiking neurons

I. INTRODUCTION

Electroencephalography (EEG) is a method to record the electrical activity of the brain. It is typically non-invasive, with the EEG electrodes placed along the scalp. The signals measured in this way represent the postsynaptic potentials of pyramidal neurons in the cortex. Since the electrical activity in the brain surface originates in the deeper brain areas that do not contribute directly to an EEG recording, their influence could be assessed accounting for the electrodes orientation and distance to the source of the activity.

By far EEG has been applied to numerous domains from brain-computer interface [1]–[3], emotion recognition [4]–[8], control of movements [9], [10], diagnostic of brain diseases [11] etc. Through the years the EEG data processing methodology has evolved from simple methods, such as mean and amplitude comparison to complicated methods, such as connectivity topology and deep learning [12], [13]. In particular, deep learning exhibits better performance in EEG classification in comparison with the conventional methods.

Nevertheless, accurate on-line classification and explanation of dynamic spatio-temporal brain data, such as EEG is still an open problem. While there are many methods introduced for brain data classification, most of them lack explainability in relation to the measured brain functions as spatio-temporal patterns.

In order to exploit EEG data for analyses the first step traditionally is to "decode" them [10], [14] or to extract a range of signal properties referred to as "features" which are then utilized for detection or classification purposes [15]. The analyses outcome is largely influenced by the quality of extracted features. A recent trend in EEG features extraction and processing exploits recurrent neural networks [11] and especially a member of reservoir family - fast on-line trainable Echo state networks (ESN) [6]–[9], [16], [17]. The reservoir computing advantage is in its training algorithms. They usually need a single training epoch by Least Squares (LS) algorithm or on-line training via the Recursive Least Squares (RLS) method. However, their randomly initialized pool of neurons does not account for brain structure so reservoir computing lacks explainability.

Accounting for spatial brain structure in the design of RNN decoders or feature extractor became a natural direction of work nowadays [4]. Recently developed brain-inspired spiking neural network (SNN) models, such as NeuCube [1]–[3], [5], [18], demonstrated a good classification accuracy and excellent explanation of the spatio-temporal patterns learned from spatio-temporal brain data, such as EEG and fMRI [19].

Recently the idea to design reservoir topology in brain-inspired manner was investigated in [4]. However, in this work the reservoir is composed by hyperbolic tangent neurons but not the brain-inspired spike timing ones. Besides the output classifier is the classical feedforward neural network trained via gradient descend method in off-line mode.

In present work we propose another combination between fast trainable reservoir computing and brain-inspired architec-

tures - the integration of the Cube of spike timing neurons module with an ESN classifier, aiming at improved classification accuracy in an on-line learning mode. The proposed method makes use of two types of information contained in the data, spike-timing, learned in an unsupervised mode in the Cube, and spike-rate or spiking frequency features, captured and classified in the ESN in an on-line mode.

Further the paper is organized as follows: section II presents briefly NeuCube and ESN structures and the proposed hierarchical architecture NeuCube-ESN for EEG on-line classification; section III presents the classification results on a benchmark example of EEG data for wrist movement and compares the achieved accuracy with NeuCube classification results from [20]; finally the concluding remarks summarize the main achievements in the presented work and points the directions for future work.

II. NEUCUBE - ESN BRAIN DATA ARCHITECTURE

A. NeuCube Structure

The NeuCube architecture is an open one, allowing for new algorithms to be explored for encoding, learning, classification, regression [21]. It consists of three parts [19]:

- Data encoding part, where input streaming data is encoded into spike sequences using a suitable algorithm [22].
- A 3D Cube structure of spiking neurons, where every neuron has a 3D spatial coordinates defined through the use of brain-template, such as Talairach or MNI or an individual one. Initial connections were generated based on small-world theory.
- SNN classifiers of evolving spiking neuron networks (eSNN) or dynamic evolving spiking neuron networks (deSNN) [23] are used to separate the outputs of NeuCube into classes.

After encoding of the spatio-temporal EEG data into sequences of spikes (spike-time information), the Cube, structured according to a brain template, receives as input EEG recordings at neurons corresponding to the electrodes' positions on the skull. As a result all neurons in the Cube generate spike trains whose dynamics depends on the input signal as well as on both the connectivity within the Cube (small world connectivity at the beginning) and on the spike time dependent plasticity of the connections (synapses). Finally the output classifier takes the Cube spike trains as classification features.

The NeuCube hyper parameters that have to be tuned are membrane potential V_{th} and refractory period t_{ref} of neurons as well as the STDP learning rate λ .

B. ESN Structure

Echo state networks (ESN) belong to a novel and rapidly developing family of reservoir computing approaches [24]–[26] whose aim was development of fast trainable recurrent neural network (RNN) architectures able to approximate nonlinear time series dependencies. The detailed structure of an ESN reservoir is shown on Fig 1.

Fig. 1. ESN reservoir structure.

It incorporates a pool of neurons with sigmoid activation function f^{res} (usually the hyperbolic tangent) that has randomly generated recurrent connection weights. The reservoir state $R(k)$ for the current time instant k depends both on its previous state $R(k-1)$ and the current input $in(k)$ as follows:

$$R(k) = (1 - a)R(k) + af^{res}(W^{in}s_{in}in(k) + W^{res}R(k-1)) \quad (1)$$

Here W^{in} is the matrix of input to reservoir connection weights that are randomly generated; W^{res} is the internal reservoir connection weight matrix that is sparse and also randomly generated according to recipes given by [25], [26], namely its spectral radius has be below 1; $a \in [0, 1]$ is leaking rate parameter and s_{in} is input scaling.

The ESN output $out(k)$ is calculated as a function f^{out} (usually identity function) of the linear combination of the current reservoir states $R(k)$ or of concatenation of the input and reservoir states $[R(k) in(k)]$ multiplied by output scaling coefficient s_{out} and weighted by the output weight matrix W^{out} :

$$out(k) = f^{out}(W^{out}s_{out}[R(k) in(k)]) \quad (2)$$

The ESN hyper parameters that are subject of manual tuning or optimized via grid search, are the reservoir size (number of neurons M), spectral radius and sparsity sp of the reservoir connection matrix and leaking rate a . The input and output scaling coefficients s_{in} and s_{out} are usually set to 1 but can be added to hyper parameters set too.

The only trainable parameters of ESN are the output weights W^{out} . In case of identity output function the least squares method is applied to train the ESN in a single iteration. For the aims of on-line training the recursive version of least squares (RLS) can be applied too [24].

C. NeuCube-ESN Brain Data Classifier

The proposed novel brain data classifier called NeuCube-ESN is a hierarchical RNN composed by two recurrent architectures - a brain inspired NeuCube, that is a spatio-temporal structure of SNN neurons and a fast trainable ESN as a nonlinear time series classifier. The overall structure is shown on Fig. 2.

In contrast to NeuCube approach, here the EEG data is scaled and fed into the Cube as generating currents into

Fig. 2. Proposed NeuCube - ESN structure.

neurons corresponding to the electrodes positions. Since the EEG sensors record the postsynaptic potential in μV , and if the resistance at measuring positions remains constant, the current sent by neural cells to their connections will be proportional to the EEG data. So feeding it at the electrode positions is equivalent to reverse engineering of the electrical activity through all brain areas.

Another difference from the NeuCube is that the output classifier (ESN) has continuous output that allows for decoding not only the types of actions but also a continuous trajectory of actions performed during EEG recording.

A 3D SNN Cube is initialised by defining the size of the Cube of N neurons and their 3D locations, including positions of EEG electrodes. The Cube is designed according to the scalable Talairach atlas [27]. Small-world connectivity method is used to derive the initial connections in the Cube, where the closer two neurons are in the 3D space, the higher the probability of them to be connected is. All synapses are plastic, i.e. they adapt their weights via Spike Timing Dependent Plasticity (STDP) rule that is a kind of unsupervised learning. Thus the achieved after feeding the input signal to the Cube connectivity will reflect the EEG data characteristics.

Spiking activity of all neurons was recorded and for a given time window D the spiking frequency of each of the N neurons in the Cube is calculated. Thus for duration of a sample EEG record of T ms a new time series of Cube firing rates is extracted as feature vector of size $T/D \times N$ as shown on Fig. 2.

The output classifier is an ESN reservoir with M neurons with properly set spectral radius of W^{res} . Its input are the generated by Cube time series (feature vectors) per given EEG sample. The initial reservoir state $R(0)$ as set to zero and its new state achieved after presentation of each EEG sample feature vector was sent to the readout. The output weights W^{out} were adjusted to predict the correct EEG class. The training was done via RLS in on-line mode.

The following Algorithm 1 depicts the functionality of the proposed classifier for E number of EEG recordings and their corresponding known class.

The connectivity obtained in the Cube SNN after presentation of each EEG sample can be analysed as spatio-temporal pattern to better understand each class of the brain activity

Algorithm 1 NeuCube-ESN

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1: Define  $N, M, T, D$ 
2: Scale EEG data
3: Create 3D Cube structure
4: Create ESN structure
for  $ee = 1 \div E$  do
5:   Connect EEG( $ee$ ) data to electrodes positions
6:    $R(0) = 0, tr = 0$ 
7:    $td = 0$ 
8:   for  $t = 1 \div T$  do
9:     Simulate Cube
10:     $td = td + 1$ 
11:    if  $td == D$  then
12:      Calculate firing rates  $FR$ 
13:       $tr = tr + 1$ 
14:       $R(tr) = f^{res}(FR, R(tr - 1))$  eq. 1
15:       $td = 0$ 
16:    end if
17:     $out = f^{out}(R(tr))$  eq. 2
18:     $error = out - class(ee)$ 
19:    Adjust  $W^{out}$  via RLS
20:  end for
21: end for

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captured as EEG data.

III. RESULTS

The benchmark data used here to illustrate the proposed method is taken from [20]. The EEG data of 14 channels *Emotiv* measuring device were collected for $T = 1000$ ms with sampling frequency of 128Hz. The test subject is asked to perform three different types of wrist movement - up, down and straight - that are separated into three EEG classes and 20 examples per class are collected, making all number of samples 60.

The 3D structure of the used Cube from the NeuCube architecture [18], [19] is shown on Fig. 2. The blue dots are neurons positions while the red dots mark the EEG electrodes positions as input neurons. The Cube is designed according to the scalable Talairach atlas [27], in this cases using $N = 1471$ neurons. The location of the input neurons, corresponding to

the used in this case 14 EEG channels, is defined following the 10-20 EEG location system.

The Cube initial randomly generated connectivity is shown on Fig. 3. The red lines correspond to excitatory connections while the blue ones - to the inhibitory connections. Initial connection weights are set to small values 80% of which positive and 20% negative.

Fig. 3. Brain template initial connections: negative inhibitory (blue) and positive excitatory (red).

The Cube is simulated in NEST Simulator, version 3.3 [28], using leaky integrate-and-fire neuron model and STDP synapses. The ESN was implemented in Python.

For the defined size of time window $D = 100$ ms the extracted time series features per EEG sample are of 1471×10 dimension. Since the ESN output is continuous value in range $[-1, 1]$, for the aim of classification the target values corresponding to three classes were $-1, 0$ and $+1$ respectively.

Fifty percents of data were used for training and the rest for testing of the classifier accuracy. K-fold cross validation was performed with $k = 6$.

In order to tune model hyper-parameters the exhaustive grid search was performed. Hyper-parameters of both modules that has to be refined and their values are given in Table I.

TABLE I
HYPER-PARAMETERS SUBJECT TO OPTIMIZATION

Parameter	Values
SNN	
V_{th}	-60, -55, -50
t_{ref}	0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5
λ	0.1, 0.01, 0.001
ESN	
a	0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8
N	3000, 3500, 4000, 4500, 5000
sp	0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8
s_{in}	0.00001, 0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1
s_{out}	0.00001, 0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1

The best Cube parameters were determined as $V_{th} = -60$, $t_{ref} = 0$, $\lambda = 0.001$. Tables II and III summarize the best

results obtained by each considered ESN reservoir size in case of NeuCube-ESN model (Table II) and only ESN model (Table III) respectively.

TABLE II
MINIMUM TEST ERROR FOR EACH SIZE OF THE ESN RESERVOIR AND BEST SNN PARAMETERS

M	sp	a	s_{in}	s_{out}	MSE_{test}
3000	0.7	0.4	1e-5	1e-5	1.589e-05
3500	0.7	0.6	1e-3	1e-2	1.358e-05
4000	0.6	0.4	1e-4	1e-2	1.590e-05
4500	0.7	0.4	1e-3	1e-5	1.360e-05
5000	0.6	0.4	1e-5	1e-2	1.292e-05

TABLE III
MINIMUM TEST ERROR FOR EACH SIZE OF THE ESN RESERVOIR WITHOUT THE SNN PRE-PROCESSING

M	sp	a	s_{in}	s_{out}	MSE_{test}
3000	0.4	0.7	1e-5	1e-2	0.013
3500	0.4	0.5	1e-5	1e-1	0.015
4000	0.4	0.5	1e-5	1e-5	0.011
4500	0.7	0.5	1e-5	1e-2	0.013
5000	0.7	0.4	1e-3	1e-2	0.018

The mean square error from test data (MSE_{test}) in tables is:

$$MSE_{test} = \sum_{i=1}^{E_{test}} \sqrt{(\hat{out}_i - out_i)^2} / E_{test} \quad (3)$$

Here E_{test} is the number of test data; \hat{out}_i is the i -th desired output of ESN and out_i is its actual value.

The minimal test errors in case of NeuCube-ESN structure is significantly smaller by orders of magnitude than in case of only ESN classifier. This result confirms the important role of the SNN brain template for features extraction from EEG data.

Figure 4 shows test data vs classification result for both considered models.

The accuracy on test data for the same benchmark EEG data set using standard NeuCube with deSNN classifier reported in [20] is 86.67%. Thus the NeuCube-ESN classifier demonstrated significantly better accuracy. An explanation might be in the encoding mechanism of the novel architecture that does not require encoding into spikes before learning which reduces the output error. Another difference that increases accuracy is that for the classification purpose NeuCube-ESN structure exploits continuous firing rate data while the deSNN classifier in [20] uses discrete spike-time information.

Fig. 5 shows connectivity changed after presentation of one EEG recording example. It is observed that the number of nonzero connections in the SNN cube decreased while the strength of left excitatory and inhibitory connections increased. The number of excitatory connections however is bigger than that of the inhibitory ones.

The SNNcube model can be interpreted in terms of patterns of connections that are learned from the data also explaining brain activity of the subject. The connectivity pattern after

Fig. 4. Test data vs both classifiers predictions.

STDP learning shown on Fig. 5 is not symmetric. Majority of the connections left are concentrated in the motor and frontal cortex where the decision of motion was taken. The excitatory connections in the visual cortex (area processing visual information) are much more than the inhibitory ones.

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed new hierarchical reservoir structure combines two types of dynamic recurrent reservoir structures - one brain-inspired spike timing Cube and another fast trainable reservoir of hyperbolic tangent neurons. In this way we integrate both spike-time and spike-rate information extracted from the data, that better represents the complexity of the EEG signals. The Cube learns the spike-timing information, while the ESN - the rate/frequency information from data, captured in the neurons of the Cube.

The proposed algorithm allows also exploration of the brain connectivity patterns obtained via reverse engineering that will contribute also to the explainability of the EEG data classification results.

Future work is planned of optimising the parameters of both the Cube and the ESN so that the model can be implemented on a neuromorphic hardware chip. The team also plans to

Fig. 5. Brain template connections after presenting only one example of EEG data: negative inhibitory (top) and positive excitatory (bottom).

apply this method on other spatio-temporal brain data, such as ECOG and fMRI.

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REFERENCES

- [1] N. Padfield, K. Camilleri, T. Camilleri, S. Fabri, M. Bugeja, A Comprehensive Review of Endogenous EEG-Based BCIs for Dynamic Device Control, *Sensors*, vol. 22 (15), 2022, art. no. 5802.
- [2] C. Ieracitano, N. Mammone, A. Hussain, F.C. Morabito, A novel explainable machine learning approach for EEG-based brain-computer interface systems, *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 34 (14), 2022, pp. 11347-11360.
- [3] S.K.R. Singanamalla, C.-T. Lin, Spike-Representation of EEG Signals for Performance Enhancement of Brain-Computer Interfaces, *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, vol. 16, 2022, art. no. 792318.
- [4] J. Zhou, T. Zhao, Y. Xie, F. Xiao, L. Sun, Emotion Recognition Based on Brain Connectivity Reservoir and Valence Lateralization for Cyber-Physical-Social Systems, *Pattern Recognition Letters*, vol. 161, 2022, pp. 154-160.
- [5] Y. Luo, Q. Fu, J. Xie, Y. Qin, G. Wu, J. Liu, F. Jiang, Y. Cao, X. Ding, EEG-Based Emotion Classification Using Spiking Neural Networks, *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, 2020, pp. 46007-46016.
- [6] R. Fourati, B. Ammar, J. Sanchez-Medina, A.M. Alimi, Unsupervised Learning in Reservoir Computing for EEG-Based Emotion Recognition, *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, vol. 13 (2), 2022, pp. 972-984.
- [7] L. Bozhkov, P. Koprinkova-Hristova, P. Georgieva, Reservoir computing for emotion valence discrimination from EEG signals, *Neurocomputing*, vol. 231, 2017, pp. 28-40.
- [8] L. Bozhkov, P. Koprinkova-Hristova, P. Georgieva, Learning to decode human emotions with Echo State Networks, *Neural Networks*, vol. 78, 2016, pp. 112-119.
- [9] Z.H. Khan, N. Hussain, M.I. Tiwana, Classification of EEG signals for wrist and grip movements using echo state network, *Biomedical Research (India)*, vol. 28 (3), 2017, pp. 1095-1102.
- [10] H. Kim, J.S. Kim, C.K. Chung, Identification of cerebral cortices processing acceleration, velocity, and position during directional reaching movement with deep neural network and explainable AI, *NeuroImage*, vol. 266, 2023, art. no. 119783.
- [11] G. Ruffini, D. Ibañez, M. Castellano, S. Dunne, A. Soria-Frisch, EEG-driven RNN classification for prognosis of neurodegeneration in at-risk patients, *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 9886, 2016, pp. 306-313.
- [12] S. Gong, K. Xing, A. Cichocki, J. Li, Deep Learning in EEG: Advance of the Last Ten-Year Critical Period, in *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive and Developmental Systems*, vol. 14, no. 2, June 2022, pp. 348-365.
- [13] S. Nakagome, A. Craik, A.S. Ravindran, Y. He, J.G. Cruz-Garza, J.L. Contreras-Vidal, J.L., Deep Learning Methods for EEG Neural Classification. In: Thakor, N.V. (eds) *Handbook of Neuroengineering*, 2023, Springer, Singapore
- [14] S. Phadikar, N. Sinha, R. Ghosh, Unsupervised feature extraction with autoencoders for EEG based multiclass motor imagery BCI, *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 213, 2023, art. no. 118901.
- [15] R. Yuvaraj, P. Thagavel, J. Thomas, J. Fogarty, F. Ali, Comprehensive Analysis of Feature Extraction Methods for Emotion Recognition from Multichannel EEG Recordings, *Sensors*, vol. 23 (2), 2023, art. no. 915.
- [16] D.-H. Jeong, J. Jeong, In-ear EEG based attention state classification using echo state network, *Brain Sciences*, vol. 10 (6), 2020, art. no. 321.
- [17] L. Sun, B. Jin, H. Yang, J. Tong, C. Liu, H. Xiong, Unsupervised EEG feature extraction based on echo state network, *Information Sciences*, vol. 475, 2019, pp. 1-17.
- [18] N.K. Kasabov, NeuCube: A Spiking Neural Network Architecture for Mapping, Learning and Understanding of Spatio-Temporal Brain Data, *Neural Networks*, vol. 52, 2014, pp. 62-76.
- [19] N.K. Kasabov, Time-Space, Spiking Neural Networks and Brain-Inspired Artificial Intelligence. 2019, Springer-Nature.
- [20] J. Hu, Z.-G. Hou, Y.-X. Chen, N. Kasabov, N. Scott, "EEG-based classification of upper-limb ADL using SNN for active robotic rehabilitation," 5th IEEE RAS/EMBS International Conference on Biomedical Robotics and Biomechatronics, Sao Paulo, Brazil, 2014, pp. 409-414.
- [21] NeuCube development environment: <https://kedri.aut.ac.nz/neucube>
- [22] B. Petro, N. Kasabov, R. Kiss, Selection and optimisation of spike encoding methods for spiking neural networks, algorithms, *IEEE Transactions of Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, vol.31, Issue 2, April 2019, pp. 358-370.
- [23] N.K. Kasabov, K. Dhoble, N. Nuntalid, G. Indiveri, Dynamic Evolving Spiking Neural Networks for Online Spatio- and spectro-temporal Pattern Recognition, *Neural Networks*, vol. 41, 2013, pp. 188-201.
- [24] H. Jaeger, Tutorial on training recurrent neural networks, covering BPPT, RTRL, EKF and the "echo state network" approach. GMD Report 159, German National Research Center for Information Technology, 2002.
- [25] C. Gallicchio, M. Lukosevicius, S. Scardapane, Frontiers in reservoir computing, Proceedings of 28th European Symposium on Artificial Neural Networks, Computational Intelligence and Machine Learning, ESANN 2020, Belgium, pp.559-566.
- [26] M. Lukosevicius, H. Jaeger, Reservoir computing approaches to recurrent neural network training, *Computer Science Review*, vol. 3, 2009, pp.127-149.
- [27] Talairach daemon: <http://www.talairach.org>
- [28] S. Spreizer et al., NEST 3.3 (3.3), 2022, Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6368024>